

Research Article

A Computer program for Calculating Crop Water Requirements

Osama Osman Ali

Department of Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Agricultural Technology and Fish Sciences,
Al -Neelain University, Sudan

ARTICLE INFO

ABSTRACT

Article No.: 121712325

DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2013.2.121712325

Submitted: 17/12/2012

Accepted: 20/01/2013

Published: 20/02/2013

***Corresponding Author**

Osama Osman Ali

E-mail:

osama12660@hotmail.com

Phone: +(249)912660468

A computer program was developed for determination of crop water requirements using local meteorological and research data, and also using Visual Basic 6.0 Programming language. For verification of the model, field trials were carried out during the period December 2007 - July 2008 at four schemes using center-pivot irrigations in the northern parts of Sudan. The program was based on using Penman equation and Penman-Monteith method. Results were comparable to those obtained through traditional time-consuming methods. The program could offer a simple tool for planning crop water requirements for agricultural projects.

Keywords:

computer program, crop water requirement, modified penman equation, penman monteith method

INTRODUCTION

Global population is expected to increase by about 30% by the year 2030, and as a result, demand for food will increase (FAO, 2000). Major constraints to meet the increasing food demands of the population, according to Ali (2008), are irrigation water and land scarcity. A possible approach to overcome constraints could be through improving performance of adopted irrigation systems or introductions of better ones.

Considerable amount of water diverted for irrigation in Sudan was not effectively used for crop production (Ahmed, 2005). It was estimated that 45% was used by crops, 15% lost in the water conveyance, 15% lost in field channels and 25% lost through inefficient field applications. Accordingly 40% of the water losses occurred at farm and field levels with direct effects on crop production due to inadequate water supplies causing water stress or excessive water that resulted in reduced growth and leaching of plant nutrients.

Crop water requirement (ET_C) is defined as the depth of water needed to meet the water loss through evapotranspiration of a disease free crop growing in large fields under non-restricting soil conditions, including soil water and fertility and achieving full production potential under the given growing environment (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1977). ET_C represents the water used by a crop for growth and cooling purposes. This water is extracted from the soil root zone by the root system and is therefore not available as stored water in the soil.

Owing to practical difficulties in obtaining accurate field measurements for ET_C prediction methods are commonly used. However, these methods often need to be applied under climatic and agronomic conditions different from those under which they were originally developed. Testing the accuracy of the methods under a new set of conditions is laborious, time consuming and costly. To overcome such difficulties, guidelines were formulated by FAO to calculate ET_C of crops under different climatic and

agronomic conditions (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1977). Nevertheless, to calculate ET_C , the effect of the following factors should be determined (Teare and Peet, 1983):

1. The effect of climate on water requirements of a reference crop:

Reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_0), is defined as the rate of evapotranspiration from an extensive surface of 8 to 15 cm tall, green grass cover of uniform height, actively growing, completely shading the ground and not short of water. ET_0 is expressed in mm per day and represents the mean value over a certain period. Methods used to estimate ET_0 include the Blaney-Criddle, Radiation, Modified-Penman, Penman-Monteith and pan evaporation. Primarily the choice of a method must be based on the type of climatic data available and on the accuracy required in determining water needs.

2. The effect of local conditions and agricultural practices on crop water requirements:

This includes the local effects of variations in climate over time, altitude, size of fields, advection, soil water availability, salinity, method of irrigation and practices, for which field data are required. Therefore, before calculating ET_C , studies carried out on crop water requirements in the area and available climatic data from meteorological and research stations should be reviewed.

3. The effect of the crop characteristics on crop water requirements:

Crop coefficient (K_c) presents the relationship between reference (ET_0) and crop evapotranspiration (ET_C). Doorenbos *et al.* (1986) stated that the value of crop coefficient (K_c) varies with crop type, developmental stage and prevailing weather conditions.

According to Doorenbos and Pruitt (1977), ET_C relates to ET_0 and K_c as follows:

$$ET_C = ET_0 \times K_c \quad 2.1$$

The equation offers a mean value for ET_C in mm per day over a specific period of time.

ET_0 could be calculated from Doorenbos and Pruitt (1977) version of Penman equation, known as Penman modified formula, as follows:

$$ET_0 = C [wR_n + (1-w).f(u).(ea-ed)] \quad 2.2$$

Where:

ET_0 = reference crop evapotranspiration (mm/day)

C = adjustment factor to compensate for the effect of day and night weather conditions

w = temperature related weighting factor

Rn = net radiation in equivalent evaporation (mm/day)

f(u) = wind related function

ea = actual vapor pressure at mean air temperature (mbar)

ed = saturation vapor pressure at mean air temperature (mbar)

Alternatively:

Reference crop evapotranspiration, according to Smith (2000), can be calculated using the Penman-Monteith equation as follows:

$$ET_0 = \frac{0.408\Delta(Rn - G) + \gamma\left(\frac{900}{T + 273}\right)U_2(ea - ed)}{\Delta + \gamma(1 + 0.34U_2)} \quad 2.3$$

Where:

ET_0 = Reference crop evapotranspiration (mm/day)

Δ = Slope of vapor pressure curve (kPa /°C)

Rn = net radiation at crop surface (MJ/m².day)

G = soil heat flux (MJ/m².day)

γ = psychometric constant (kPa /°C)

T = average temperature at 2 meter height (°C)

U = wind speed at 2 meter height (m/s)

ea = saturation vapour pressure (kPa)

ed = actual vapour pressure (kPa)

To ease calculation of ET_C using local research and meteorological data, the objectives of this work was to establish a simple computer program for calculating ET_C using the modified penman equation and Penman-Monteith method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The programming language of Visual Basic, version 6.0 was used to develop the program for calculating crop water requirements using the modified Penman equation and the Penman-Monteith method. It was based on five flow charts. The first chart is a welcoming screen and loads the database for the program (Fig.1). The other four flow charts calculate ET_0 , K_c and ET_C using the modified Penman equation or the Penman-Monteith method according to the choice of the user (Fig.2.1, Fig.2.2, Fig.2.3 and Fig.3).

The program was tested using factual data from three sites within the Nile State (North of Khartoum) that were adopting center - pivot irrigation systems. The general texture of the soil in the Estate was sandy clay loam. A fourth site of a heavy clay soil from Khartoum area, used by Arab Company for Agric. Crops grown there was Alfalfa and onions. Sites in the Nile Estate were:

1. Ras Al Wadi Alakhdar Project: The Project lies about 17 km north of Atbra town. The main crop was Alfalfa.
2. El Bashair Jordanian Company: The project was approximately 29.5 km south El Damar town. The main crop was onions.
3. Tala Company for Investment project in Shendi area: The main crop was Alfalfa.

Program Flow Charts

Fig 1: Flow chart to load main format for data entry.

Fig 2.1: Flow chart for calculating ET_c using Modified Penman equation.

Fig 2.2: Flow chart for calculating ETc Using Modified Penman equation

Fig 2.3: Flow chart for calculating ET_c using Modified Penman equation.

Fig 3: Flow chart for calculating ET_c using Penman-Monteith Method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Plates 1 to 3 show windows displayed during operation of the program and Table 1 to 8 show values of ET_0 and ET_c as calculated by the program using data from the four test sites, and Table 9 to 11 show Agrometeorological data.

El Bashair and Ras Al Wadi Al akhadar gave highest ET_0 (8.7mm/day and 8.9mm/day respectively) with the modified Penman equation and Penman-Monteith method, followed by Tala Project and Arab Company. That was because temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and sunshine hours were greater in the former than in the latter projects. Generally, the

highest readings in each project were obtained in May with April following closely behind. January, February and March gave lower values in Penman-Monteith method compared to the modified Penman equation. Results obtained through the program were comparable to those obtained by Ali (2002) who found crop evapotranspiration of 8.9 mm/day in West Omdurman when using the modified Penman equation and Ahmed (2005) who found ETo of 7.2 mm/day

when using Penman-Monteith equation in New Halfa area.

CONCLUSION

The proposed computer model offered a simple and effective tool for calculating crop water requirements using the modified Penman equation and the Penman-Monteith method.

Table 1: Crop water requirement estimation using modified Penman equation (Ras Al Wadi Alakhdar Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 17°N Altitude = 294 m	Jan.	5.7	6.8
	Feb.	6.4	7.7
	March	7.1	8.5
	April	8.1	9.7
	May	8.7	10.4

Table 2: Crop water requirement estimation using Penman- Monteith equation (Ras Al Wadi Alakhdar Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 17°N Elevation = 294 m	Jan.	4.9	5.9
	Feb.	5.3	6.4
	March	6.7	8.0
	April	8.1	9.7
	May	8.9	10.6

Table 3: Crop water requirement estimation using modified Penman equation (El Bashair Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Onion Direction = North Latitude = 17°N Altitude = 364 m	Jan.	5.7	6.0
	Feb.	6.4	6.7
	March	7.1	7.4
	April	8.1	8.5
	May	8.7	9.1

Table 4: Crop water requirement estimation using Penman-Monteith equation (El Bashair Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Onion Direction = North Latitude = 17°N Elevation = 364 m	Jan.	4.9	5.2
	Feb.	5.3	5.6
	March	6.7	7.0
	April	8.1	8.5
	May	8.9	9.3

Table 5: Crop water requirement estimation using modified Penman equation (Tala Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 16°N Altitude = 360 m	Jan.	4.8	5.8
	Feb.	6.1	7.3
	March	7.4	8.9
	April	8.4	10.1
	May	8.6	10.3

Table 6: Crop water requirement estimation using Penman- Monteith equation (Tala Project)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 16°N Elevation = 360 m	Jan.	5.1	6.1
	Feb.	5.8	6.9
	March	7.0	8.4
	April	8.0	9.9
	May	8.4	10.0

Table 7: Crop water requirement estimation using modified Penman equation (Arab company)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 15°N Altitude = 387 m	Jan.	4.8	5.8
	Feb.	6.4	7.7
	March	7.6	9.1
	April	8.0	9.6
	May	8.4	10.0

Table 8: Crop water requirement estimation using Penman- Monteith equation (Arab company)

Input data		Output data	
Data	Month	ETo mm/day	ETc mm/day
Crop = Alfalfa Direction = North Latitude = 15°N Elevation = 387 m	Jan.	5.1	6.1
	Feb.	6.1	7.3
	March	6.9	8.3
	April	7.9	9.5
	May	8.0	9.6

Table 9: Agrometeorological data

Month	Min. Temp. °C	Max. Temp. °C	Mean RH%	Mph day	Mph night	Sunshine (h)
Jan.	14.9	29.2	32	2.74	2.37	9.1
Feb.	15.9	31.3	31	2.88	2.63	9.9
Mar.	20.9	38.6	23	2.72	1.54	10.2
April	25.2	40.4	23	2.64	2.33	9.2
May	25.7	41.4	18	2.50	2.18	9.1

Source: Shambat meteorological Station (2008).

Table 10: Agrometeorological data

Month	Min. Temp. °C	Max. Temp. °C	Mean RH%	Mph day	Mph night	Sunshine (h)
Jan.	20.2	14.5	50	3.2	3.61	10.1
Feb.	31	14.8	47	2.97	2.63	10.3
Mar.	33.4	19.2	30	2.85	2.52	10.3
April.	36.5	24.9	27	2.86	2.69	10.7
May	44	25.4	12	2.93	2.13	10.8

Source: Hedaba meteorological Station (2008).

Table 11: Agrometeorological data

Month	Min. Temp. °C	Max. Temp. °C	Mean RH%	Mph day	Mph night	Sunshine (h)
Jan.	13.6	29.1	44	3.2	3.61	10.1
Feb.	12.4	31.5	36	2.97	2.63	10.3
Mar.	18.3	38.7	29	2.85	2.52	10.3
April	22.9	40.9	27	2.86	2.13	10.7
May	23.2	42.8	24	2.93	2.69	10.8

Source: Shandi meteorological Station (2008).

Plate 1: Main Window

Plate 2: Crop water requirement (Penman-Monteith)

Plate 3: Crop water requirement (Modified Penman)

Year	Month	MinTempC	MaxTempC	MeanRh	MphDay	MphNight	Sunshine_h
2005	1	13.5	29.7	26	10	8	10.3
2005	2	16.2	31.9	23.7	7	6	10
2005	3	20.3	40.3	28	6	5	10
2005	4	22.7	41.2	26	8	6	10.2
2005	5	25	42	27	7	5	9.1
2005	6	24.8	41.3	21	6	5	11.2
2005	7	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2005	8	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2005	9	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2005	10	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2005	11	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2005	12	13.5	29.7	26	6	8	10.3
2006	7	17	52	26	6	8	10.3
2006	8	18	54	26	6	8	10.3
2006	9	30	43	26	6	8	10.3
2006	10	44	46	26	6	8	10.3
2006	11	40	45	26	6	8	10.3
2006	12	34	34	0	0	0	0
2008	1	14.5	20.2	50	3.2	3.61	10.1
2008	2	14.8	31	47	2.97	2.63	10.3
2008	3	19.2	33.4	30	2.85	2.52	10.3
2008	4	24.9	36.5	27	2.86	2.69	10.7
2008	5	25.4	44	12	2.93	2.13	10.8

Plate 4.4: Agrometeorological Data (Sample Data)

REFERENCES

- FAO (2000). Yearbook. Production. Vol. 55. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- Wayne DC and Haise HR (1957). Irrigation in arid regions. The Year Book of Agric. The U.S. Department of Agriculture, Washington.
- Ali OO (2002). Evaluation of the performance of centre pivot irrigation system. M.Sc. Thesis, University of Khartoum, Sudan.
- Ali. O.O.(2008). A Simulation model for centre pivot irrigation system design and optimization of operation. PhD. Thesis, University of Khartoum, Sudan.
- Ahmed TA (2005). Response of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) growth and yield to different irrigation regimes and tillage systems under New Halfa area conditions. Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Khartoum.
- Doorenbos J and Pruitt WO (1977). Crop water requirement. FAO Irrigation and Drainage, Paper No. (24), FAO, Rome, Italy.
- Teare ID and Peet MM (1983). Crop water relations. A Wiley Inter-Science Publication, USA.
- Doorenbos J, Kassam AH, Bentrelsen CLM, BranscheidV, Ptusje JMGA, Smith M, Uittenbogaard GO and Van Der Wall HK (1986). Yield response to water FAO. Irrigation and Drainage, Paper No.33.
- Smith M (2000). The application of climatic data for planning and management of sustainable rainfed and irrigated crop production. Agricultural and Forest Meteorology.